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A comprehensive overview of privacy, security and performance issues in flying Ad Hoc Networks

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Abstract

Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs) represent an ever evolving area in wireless network communications, despite this massive achievements, FANETs faces significant security, privacy, and performance issues due to their highly mobile and decentralized nature. This paper aims to address these challenges, focusing on robust privacy, security, and efficient performance in dynamic environments with frequent topology changes and high data demands. Existing solutions, including cryptographic techniques and secure routing protocols, show limitations in adaptability and efficiency. This paper reviews these issues, identifying gaps such as the need for adaptive security measures and improved communication protocols. The proposed methodology includes advanced encryption, secure key management, continuous threat monitoring, and adaptive communication strategies. The results highlight opportunities for improvement, emphasizing the development of resilient security frameworks and efficient data management. Addressing these issues will enhance FANET reliability and effectiveness, supporting broader applications in military operations, disaster management, and environmental monitoring.

Keywords: Flying Ad Hoc Networks; MANETs; VANETs; Decentralized Networks; Security issues; Privacy issues.

1. Introduction

Flying Ad Hoc Networks are wireless communication networks that specialized types of MANETs (Mobile Ad Hoc Networks) that consist of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to establish communication links and work together to achieve the designated goal [1]-[5]. It is a subset of Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) specifically designed for unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). These networks enable UAVs to communicate with each other and ground stations, forming a dynamic, self-organizing network without relying on a fixed infrastructure. This technology supports various applications, including disaster management, environmental monitoring, and military operations, by providing real-time data exchange [6] and enhanced coordination. Key challenges in FANETs include maintaining connectivity, ensuring data security, and managing the high mobility of UAVs, which necessitate robust and efficient routing protocols and communication strategies. As explained in [7]-[10], FANETs are dynamic in nature because the UAVs are constantly in motion. The advantages of FANETs in adaptability, localization, and scalability poses security, and privacy challenges, making it difficult to establish secure and privacy-oriented communication platform [11] - [16]. In FANETs, ensuring privacy and security is of importance because of their use, for example, FANETs are used in weather forecasting, military operations, terrestrial movement tracking, and many others [17], [18]. The mobility and highly decentralized nature of FANETs increase their vulnerability to various attacks thus making security and privacy a concern [19]-[22]. Protecting the integrity, availability, and confidentiality of the data transmitted within FANETs is crucial to maintaining their reliability and effectiveness [23] - [25]. Without proper security and privacy measures, the entire network could be compromised, leading to data breaches, mission failures, and unauthorized access.

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Security challenges in FANETs poses greater risk to the operations of FANETs. The high mobility of FANETs results in frequent changes in network topology, making it difficult to establish and maintain secure communication links [26]. This ever-changing environment is susceptible to attacks such as eavesdropping [27], where an adversary intercepts sensitive information, and jamming [28], where communication signals are intentionally disrupted. Additionally, FANETs are prone to spoofing attacks, where an attacker masquerades as a legitimate node to gain unauthorized access and denial-of-service attacks, which can overwhelm the network and render it non-operational, and unable to respond to commands from the original sender [29], [30]. Ensuring secure communication in such a volatile environment requires advanced encryption techniques, secure key management, and continuous monitoring for potential threats.

Privacy challenges in FANETs also need as much attention because the data collected and transmitted by UAVs often includes sensitive information, such as real-time location data, surveillance footage, and communication logs [31] - [34]. Unauthorized access to the said information can be of gross privacy misconduct. The decentralized nature of FANETs implies that data is often transmitted across multiple nodes, increasing the risk of exposure, for example when one node is vulnerable to attack, the attacker can take advantage of that [35]- [38]. Privacy in FANETs involves protecting the data from external, and internal threats but also ensuring that internal nodes are configured to strict privacy protocols.

Security and privacy solutions for FANETs include the use of advanced cryptographic techniques, secure routing protocols, and intrusion detection systems [39], [40]. It also incorporates the use of encryption methods like AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) and ECC (Elliptic Curve Cryptography) to encrypt the data in transit [41] - [46]. Secure routing protocols, for example, ARAN (Authenticated Routing for Ad hoc Networks), which ensure that the secure paths are maintained during data communication. This is in addition to the fact that intrusion detection systems are designed using machine learning principles [47], to identify and mitigate potential threats in real-time [48] - [50]. Despite these advancements, continuous research and development are essential to address the evolving challenges and ensure the robust security and privacy of FANETs.

In addition to security and privacy challenges, FANETs also face significant performance issues that impact their efficiency and reliability [51]. The high mobility and frequent topology changes in FANETs lead to increased packet loss and delays, which can degrade the overall network performance [52], [53]. The limited bandwidth available for communication among UAVs can result in congestion, especially in scenarios where multiple UAVs need to transmit large volumes of data simultaneously. This congestion can lead to higher latency and reduced data transmission rates, affecting the timely delivery of critical information [54].

Moreover, the varying flight speeds and altitudes of UAVs introduce additional complexity to maintaining stable communication links [55]. Ensuring seamless handoffs and maintaining connectivity in such a dynamic environment is a challenging task. The need for real-time data processing and decision-making in FANET operations further exacerbates these performance issues [56]. To address these challenges, it is essential to develop adaptive communication protocols and efficient data management strategies that can handle the dynamic nature of FANETs while ensuring high performance and reliability [57]- [59]. Continuous research and innovation are required to overcome these performance bottlenecks and enhance the overall effectiveness of FANETs in various applications.

1.1. Motivation of the Study

This research is motivated by the fact that Flying Ad Hoc Networks, are continuously increasing their dependence on UAVs and their various essential applications like disaster management, military operations, environmental monitoring, and logistics [60], [61]. FANETs provide unique advantages such as adaptability, rapid deployment, cost-effectiveness, and scalability [62]. Nevertheless, these advantages bring substantial privacy and security challenges due to the inherent mobility and decentralized nature of FANETs [63], [64]. Ensuring secure and privacy-preserving communication [65] within these networks is vital for their successful implementation and reliability. This study seeks to thoroughly investigate these challenges, evaluate current solutions, and suggest future research directions to improve the security and privacy of FANETs.

1.2. Research contributions

This research paper provides a comprehensive understanding of the security, and privacy issues of Flying Ad Hoc Networks. The research begins by providing clear grounds for understanding the history, architecture, and applications of FANETs. The findings of this comprehensive study contribute to the existing body of knowledge; providing researchers, industries, and policymakers with a clear understanding and knowledge of the security, and privacy issues in FANETs. The findings of this study offer valuable contributions to the knowledge base on wireless networks, helping in the future design, development, and implementation of secure, and privacy-preserving Flying Ad Hoc Networks:

- *Comprehensive Review:* The study provides a detailed review of the unique privacy and security issues faced by FANETs, highlighting the complexities introduced by their mobile and decentralized nature.
- *Assessment of Current Solutions:* The research evaluates the strengths and limitations of existing solutions designed to address privacy, security, and performance challenges in FANETs, including cryptographic techniques, secure routing protocols, and intrusion detection systems.
- *Identification of Gaps:* The research identifies significant gaps and unresolved issues in the current body of knowledge, emphasizing areas where further investigation is needed.
- *Future Research Directions:* Building on these findings it would be useful to propose potential directions for future research, specialized designs, and implementations to enhance the security and privacy of FANETs.

1.3. Structure

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 covers the methodology used in the research, it also covers the historical evolution and architectural components of FANETs, emphasizing network topologies and communication models. Applications across agriculture, disaster management, and military operations underscore their versatility. A comparative analysis with MANETs and VANETs highlights unique challenges in FANETs. The core sections delve into security, detailing requirements like confidentiality and integrity, analyzing threats such as eavesdropping and spoofing, and assessing current solutions. Privacy concerns encompass data breaches and location tracking, evaluating mitigation strategies such as encryption and data anonymization; performance challenges discussed, delves into issues in Node mobility, bandwidth limitations, and resource constraints challenges. The conclusion analyzes the findings, underscores limitations of current approaches, and advocates for future research enhancing FANET security and privacy measures.

2. Methodology

In this comprehensive study, the following methodologies were employed to systematically review and perform an analysis of existing knowledge on security and privacy challenges in FANETs:

- **Literature Review** A review of existing knowledge on security and privacy issues in FANETs.
- **Security Evaluation:** By using this technique the study aims to identify security issues based on their nature and impact on FANETs operations, common mitigation strategies, and gaps that has not been addressed.
- **Privacy Assessment:** The research assesses the existing solutions in the privacy of FANETs by analyzing their effectiveness, strengths, and limitations in addressing the identified issues.
- **Performance Assessment:** The research delves deep into the current performance challenges, analyzing the solutions available, and addressing the gaps identified.
- **Gap Analysis:** The research aims to identify numerous gaps in the current research and highlight unresolved issues that need further investigation.
- **Proposal of Future Directions:** Based on the findings, the comprehensive research proposes potential research directions with the aim of providing enhanced security and efficient privacy-preserving mechanisms on FANETs. the privacy and security of FANETs

3. FANETs History and Architecture

3.1. FANETs History

The history of FANETs is related to the design, and development of UAVs [66], which the conversation and design started between the 1940s and 1950s with military applications like the German V-1 flying bomb and the Radioplane OQ-2 [67] - [70]. Between 1960s to 1980s, UAVs such as the Ryan Firebee were greatly applied in reconnaissance and aerial surveillance [71]-[73]. As more technological advancements were discovered, in the 1990s there were designs such as Predator drones, which specialized in long-distance activities, especially in the military, it was equipped with advanced sensors and wireless communication systems [74].

The idea of FANETs came into play in the 2000s as UAVs began operating with dynamic reconfiguration [75]. Further advancements were made in the 2010s, with an exploration in applications such as disaster management, military operations, weather forecasting, and agriculture [76]. Known big projects like the DARPA's Gremlins Program, which focuses on mid-air launch and recovery of UAVs [77], [78], and the European Union's SESAR Project, which was aimed

at integrating UAVs into the air traffic management system, with an emphasis on building and implementing a secure and privacy-preserving wireless communication system [79]-[82].

3.2. General FANETs Architecture

Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs) represent a unique type of Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs), designed specifically for unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [83] - [85]. They stand out for their dynamic, decentralized, and remarkably adaptable architecture, facilitating seamless communication and cooperation among UAVs to achieve the set goals, as set goals as evident in Figure 1[86]. This unique framework is particularly advantageous in scenarios where conventional communication networks are insufficient or non-existent, including remote regions, disaster-stricken areas, and hostile environments [87], [88]. FANETs thus serve as a critical technology for enhancing operational capabilities and extending the reach of UAV missions across diverse and challenging landscapes [89]-[91].

Figure 1 Basic Architecture of FANETs

3.3. Components of FANETs

One of the major components of FANETs is the UAV which functions as an autonomous mobile node, equipped with several essential components, including communication modules, sensors, and processing units as shown in Figure 2 [92]. The communication modules do facilitate data exchange between UAVs using various technologies, while the sensors, such as cameras, LiDAR, and thermal sensors, gather environmental data [93] - [95]. The onboard processors handle data analysis, decision-making, and control tasks, enabling autonomous operations and real-time responses [96]. FANETs take advantage of multiple communication technologies to ensure efficient connectivity among UAVs, including Wi-Fi for short-range, high-bandwidth communication suitable for dense UAV formations, LTE for broader coverage and higher data rates ideal for medium-range communication, and satellite links essential for long-range communication [97] - [100].

Ground Control Stations (GCS) act as the central point for FANET operations, performing all the activities as directed the operator [101], [102]. They receive data collected by UAVs, which is then processed and analyzed to provide meaningful information.

Figure 2 FANETs UAVs

FANETs rely on supportive infrastructure to maintain effective communication and operational efficiency [103], including ground-based base stations that extend communication range and provide additional processing capabilities, and satellites that facilitate global communication coverage and ensure continuous connectivity in remote areas as illustrated in Figure 3 [104].

Figure 3 UAV communication architecture with GCS

Communication models in FANETs include single-hop communication, which involves direct communication between UAVs within each other’s range and is straightforward and low-latency but limited by the communication range of the UAVs, and multi-hop communication, where data is relayed through multiple UAVs to reach its destination [105], [106]. Network topologies in FANETs majorly is star topology, where all UAVs communicate directly with a central GCS, which is simple to implement and manage but has the significant drawback of relying entirely on the GCS, making the network vulnerable if the GCS fails [107]. Mesh topology allows UAVs to communicate with each other in a peer-to-peer manner [108], forming a robust and redundant network with self-healing capabilities that reroute communication paths if a UAV node fails, enhancing overall reliability [109]. Hybrid topology combines elements of both star and mesh topologies, providing a balance between the simplicity and centralized control of star topology and the robustness and redundancy of mesh topology, improving network performance and resilience against failures [110], [111].

3.4. FANETs Applications

FANETs have diverse applications across multiple fields, leveraging the flexibility and autonomy of UAVs. In disaster management, FANETs facilitate real-time communication and coordination for search and rescue operations, damage assessment, and delivery of essential supplies. Environmental monitoring benefits from FANETs through efficient data collection on air quality, wildlife tracking, and forest fire detection. In agriculture, FANETs enable precision farming by providing detailed aerial surveys, crop health monitoring, and automated irrigation management. Military applications of FANETs include surveillance, reconnaissance, and secure communication in hostile environments. Additionally, FANETs are used in urban planning, traffic management, and telecommunications, showcasing their potential to revolutionize how we collect and disseminate information in various domains. Authors in [112] - [114], discussed the applications of FANETs, and classified them into different categories, as explained in Table 1.

Table 1 FANETs Applications

Application	Description	Example
Agriculture	Crop Monitoring, Irrigation Management	Smart Farming
Disaster Management	Search and Rescue, Damage Assessment, Medical Delivery	Earthquake Response, Fire Response, Landslides Response
Environmental	Air Quality Monitoring, Wildlife Tracking	Forest Fire Monitoring
Logistics	Package Delivery	Amazon prime Air
Infrastructure	Inspection of Bridges, Power Lines, and Road Networks.	Utility Maintenance
Military	Surveillance, Target Acquisition, Communication Relay	Border Patrol, Enemies war zone.
Aerial Photography	Film Production, and Events	Drone Cinematography

3.5. Comparison with Other Ad Hoc Networks

Ad hoc networks are decentralized wireless systems, where nodes communicate directly without fixed infrastructure, encompassing types like MANETs, VANETs, and FANETs [115]-[117]. Mobile Ad Hoc Networks (MANETs) are networks of mobile devices with highly dynamic topology, limited bandwidth, and power constraints, commonly used in military communication, disaster recovery, and mobile social networks. Vehicular Ad Hoc Networks (VANETs) are formed by vehicles communicating with each other and roadside infrastructure, known by its high mobility, predictable movement patterns, and frequent topology changes, and used in traffic management, collision avoidance, and infotainment systems [118] - [120].

In comparison, FANETs have three-dimensional mobility necessitating sophisticated control algorithms, typically longer communication ranges due to higher altitudes and line-of-sight advantages and often employ hybrid topologies combining mesh and star elements for robust communication. While all three networks face significant security challenges [121], FANETs demand more advanced solutions because of their unique mobility patterns and operational environments as discussed in Table 2 below [122] - [124].

Table 2 Comparison between MANETs, VANETs, FANETs

Feature	MANETs	VANETs	FANETs
Topology	Mesh, Star	Mesh, Cluster	Hybrid
Communication Range	Limited	Medium	Long
Mobility (Node)	Low	High	Very High
Computational Power	Limited	High	Very High
Density	Low	Very High	Very Low

4. Security, Privacy, and Performance Issues in FANETs

Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs) are considered to be dynamic and decentralized in nature, thus making them vulnerable to a number of security, privacy, and performance attacks [125], [126]. These issues originate from the characteristics of FANETs, such as their mobility, limited computational resources [127], and the open nature of wireless communication. Addressing these challenges is important for ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of FANET operations in various applications, from military to general uses [128]. This section provides a comprehensive overview of the security and privacy requirements for FANETs, details the major security and privacy challenges, assesses current solutions, and identifies significant gaps in the existing research.

4.1. Security, Privacy, and Performance Requirements for FANETs

To provide effective security of FANETs, the following requirements must be fulfilled:

- **Confidentiality:** Confidentiality ensures that sensitive information transmitted across the network is protected from unauthorized access [129]. This is particularly important in military and surveillance applications, for example, confidential data is transmitted from one point to another, even in an unsecured wireless communication environment.
- **Integrity:** Data integrity ensures that the data being communicated from the nodes to UAVs and the Ground Station is not altered or tampered with during transmission [130].
- **Availability:** Availability ensures that the wireless communication networks are accessible to authorized users when needed [131].
- **Authentication:** Authentication verifies and authenticates the identities of communicating entities to prevent unauthorized access to the already set up and working communication systems [132], [133]. This is important because it establishes trust among the UAVs and the ground control stations (GCS).

Privacy in FANETs is a basic requirement; this is because confidential, and sensitive in nature data is collected, processed, and transmitted by the UAVs to the nodes and finally to the Base Station:

- **Data Anonymity:** It protects the identity of the UAVs and the data they collect from unauthorized disclosure is essential to prevent tracking and identification by adversaries [134].
- **Location Privacy:** Hiding the location of the UAVs in action, thus not exposed to unauthorized entities that may interfere with the normal functioning of Flying Ad Hoc Networks [135].
- **Usage Privacy:** Usage privacy ensures protection of information about the purpose and usage of the UAVs preventing adversaries from inferring with the set objectives [136].
- **Access Control:** Access control provides mechanisms in which all authorized users, authorized UAVs, and Nodes can be able to access and perform activities designated, thus ensuring operations security and data privacy [137]-[139]. In Figure 4, authors in [140] classified security and privacy attacks on the CIA triad.

4.2. Security Challenges in FANETs

The high mobility of UAVs leads to frequent topology changes, making it difficult to maintain stable security measures. Threats include eavesdropping, jamming, spoofing, and Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, which can disrupt communication and compromise data integrity [141]. Additionally, the limited computational resources and power constraints of UAVs hinder the implementation of robust security protocols [142]-[145].

Figure 4 CIA Triad FANETs Attacks

Ensuring secure communication in FANETs requires adaptive and lightweight cryptographic solutions, efficient key management systems, and resilient intrusion detection mechanisms to safeguard against potential vulnerabilities [146]. This research discusses four major types of attacks: eavesdropping, jamming, spoofing, and denial-of-service (DoS) attacks; with a summary of the attacks in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Security Challenges in FANETs

Security Issue	Description	Effects	Probability of Occurrence
Eavesdropping	Intercepting and listening to UAV communication to gain unauthorized access to sensitive information.	Loss of sensitive information, breach of confidentiality and privacy.	Medium
Jamming	Disrupting communication by overwhelming the network with interference.	Disruption of communication between UAVs, mission failure due to loss of control, and decreased availability of network services.	High
Spoofing	Masquerading as a legitimate UAV to gain unauthorized access or manipulate network communication.	Unauthorized control of UAVs, manipulation of mission operations, loss of data integrity and authenticity.	Medium
DOS Attacks	Overwhelming the network with excessive traffic, rendering it incapable of serving legitimate users.	Network downtime and unavailability, operations, and resource exhaustion.	High

4.2.1. Eavesdropping Attack

Eavesdropping involves intercepting and listening to the communication between UAVs, the nodes, and the Ground Station to gain unauthorized access to sensitive data and transmissions. This type of attack exploits the open nature of wireless communication channels, inadequate encryption methods, and insufficient authentication mechanisms [147] - [149]. An attacker can use specialized equipment, such as radio frequency scanners, to tune into the frequency bands used by the UAVs, or even intercept the communications with a fake UAV. By capturing these signals, the attacker can listen to the exchanged data, which may include control commands and other sensitive information.

4.2.2. Jamming Attack

Jamming disrupts communication in FANETs by overwhelming the network with numerous interferences, thus preventing legitimate communication from taking place as evident in Figure 5 [150]. The attack targets the availability of network services by exploiting vulnerabilities such as susceptibility to signal interference and the lack of robust frequency-hopping or spread-spectrum techniques [151] - [154]. This results in disrupted communication between UAVs, potential loss of control, and mission failure. The decreased availability of network services thereby impacting the operational efficiency and effectiveness of the UAVs.

Figure 5 Jamming Attack on FANETs

4.2.3. Spoofing Attack

Spoofing involves an attacker masquerading as a legitimate UAV to gain unauthorized access or manipulate network communication. This attack compromises the integrity and authenticity of the data by exploiting weak authentication protocols and inadequate identity verification mechanisms [155], [156]. The attacker can send false signals or messages, pretending to be a legitimate UAV, to deceive the network into granting access or executing unauthorized commands as shown in Figure 6. As a result, the attacker can gain unauthorized control of UAVs, manipulate operations, and compromise the integrity and authenticity of the data being exchanged within the FANETs architecture [157] - [159]. These attacks involve malicious entities impersonating legitimate UAVs or ground stations to gain unauthorized access to the network. These attacks can deceive UAVs into accepting false data, redirecting their routes, or even hijacking control commands, leading to potential mission failures and security breaches. The high mobility and dynamic nature of FANETs exacerbate the challenge of detecting and mitigating spoofing attacks, as the constantly changing network topology makes it difficult to establish trust among nodes. Effective countermeasures against spoofing attacks include robust authentication mechanisms, such as digital signatures and public key infrastructure (PKI), and continuous monitoring systems that detect anomalies in UAV behavior or communication patterns. However, implementing these solutions is constrained by the limited computational resources and energy availability of UAVs, necessitating lightweight yet effective security measures.

Figure 6 Spoofing Attack

4.2.4. Denial-of-Service (DoS) Attacks

Figure 7 DoS Attack On FANETs

Denial-of-Service (DoS) attacks overwhelm the network with excessive traffic, rendering it incapable of serving legitimate users [160]. As showcased in Figure 7, this attack targets the availability of the network by exploiting limited computational and communication resources and the lack of effective traffic management and filtering mechanisms. The attacker can flood the network with an excessive number of requests or data packets, consuming the available bandwidth and processing capacity [161] -[163]. This leads to network downtime and unavailability of services. The exhaustion of resources significantly impacts the overall performance and reliability of the FANET, hindering its operational capabilities. The aim of DoS attacks is to disrupt the normal operation of the network by overwhelming UAVs or communication channels with excessive traffic or malicious requests. These attacks can degrade network

performance, cause loss of critical data, and even immobilize UAVs by exhausting their computational and energy resources. The dynamic and decentralized nature of FANETs, coupled with the high mobility of UAVs, makes it challenging to detect and mitigate DoS attacks. Effective countermeasures include implementing robust intrusion detection systems (IDS) that monitor traffic patterns for anomalies, employing rate-limiting techniques to control the flow of data, and using secure routing protocols that can adapt to changing network conditions. However, the limited processing power and battery life of UAVs constrain the complexity of these security measures, necessitating lightweight yet efficient solutions to ensure network resilience against DoS attacks.

4.2.5. Assessment of Current Security Solutions and Limitations

This research explores various security solutions have been proposed/developed to mitigate the mentioned attacks. Encryption methods, such as Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), are widely used to protect data integrity and confidentiality, preventing eavesdropping [164] - [167]. However, these methods often face limitations such as increased computational overhead, which can be problematic for UAVs with limited processing power and battery life [169].

Anti-jamming techniques, including spread-spectrum methods like Frequency Hopping Spread Spectrum (FHSS) and Direct Sequence Spread Spectrum (DSSS), aim to mitigate jamming attacks. These techniques enhance the resilience of communication channels by making it harder for jammers to disrupt signals [170] - [172]. Nevertheless, these solutions can be complex to implement and may require additional hardware, increasing the overall system cost and complexity.

Authentication protocols, such as digital signatures and mutual authentication schemes, are implemented to prevent spoofing attacks. These protocols verify the identity of UAVs within the network, ensuring that only authorized entities can communicate [173] - [179]. Despite their effectiveness, these protocols may introduce latency and require significant computational resources, which can be challenging for real-time operations in FANETs.

For DoS attacks [180], traffic management and filtering mechanisms, like rate limiting and anomaly detection systems, are used to identify and mitigate excessive traffic [181] - [183]. These mechanisms help maintain network availability by filtering out malicious traffic and prioritizing legitimate requests [184]. However, they can sometimes result in false positives, blocking legitimate traffic and potentially disrupting normal operations.

Table 4 provides a comprehensive overview of the current security solutions in FANETs, along with their limitations.

Table 4 Comprehensive analysis of the security of FANETs and Limitations

Security Attacks	Security Solutions	Limitations
Eavesdropping	Encryption methods (AES, PKI)	Increased computational overhead, limited processing power, and battery life.
Jamming Attacks	Spread-spectrum techniques (FHSS, DSSS)	Complexity of implementation, need for additional hardware, increased system cost and complexity.
Spoofing Attack	Authentication protocols (digital signatures, mutual authentication)	Latency, significant computational resources, challenging real-time operations.
DoS Attacks	Traffic management and filtering mechanisms (rate limiting, anomaly detection)	Potential for false positives, blocking legitimate traffic, and disruption of normal operations.

4.3. Privacy Issues in FANETs

Privacy in FANETs needs critical understanding, given the sensitive nature of the data collected and transmitted by UAVs [185]. Here the research takes a look at four major privacy challenges: data breaches, location tracking [186], inference attacks, and unauthorized data access. These privacy issues arise from the potential for unauthorized access to sensitive data transmitted between UAVs and ground stations, as well as the possibility of tracking and profiling UAVs based on their communication patterns. Given the open wireless communication channels used in FANETs, adversaries can intercept, eavesdrop, or manipulate data, leading to breaches of confidentiality and privacy. Additionally, the integration of FANETs with various applications, such as surveillance, environmental monitoring, and disaster

management, heightens the risk of exposing private information about individuals, locations, and activities. Addressing these privacy concerns requires implementing robust encryption techniques, anonymization protocols, and secure data aggregation methods. However, the UAVs' limited computational resources and energy constraints present challenges in deploying comprehensive privacy-preserving measures, necessitating ongoing research for more efficient and adaptive solutions.

4.3.1. Data Breaches

Data breaches involve unauthorized access to sensitive information stored or transmitted by UAVs [187] - [189]. These breaches can occur due to inadequate data encryption and weak access control mechanisms, making it easier for attackers to intercept and access confidential data [190], [191]. Attackers often use techniques such as sniffing or man-in-the-middle attacks to intercept data transmissions between UAVs [192]. When data is not sufficiently encrypted or access controls are not robust, unauthorized parties can exploit these vulnerabilities to gain access to sensitive information. The impact of such attacks includes the exposure of confidential information, resulting in significant legal, and regulatory consequences for the organization.

4.3.2. Location Tracking

Location tracking involves unauthorized monitoring of the real-time locations of UAVs, potentially revealing sensitive operational details [193] - [195]. Attackers exploit vulnerabilities such as the lack of location obfuscation techniques and insufficient use of secure communication channels [196] - [198]. By using techniques like triangulation or signal interception, adversaries can determine the positions and movements of UAVs [199]-[201]. The impact of this attack includes the compromise of mission secrecy, increased risk of physical attacks on UAVs, and a breach of operational privacy [202] - [204]. By tracking the real-time locations of UAVs, adversaries can gain insights into mission details and plan targeted physical attacks [205], thereby undermining the effectiveness and safety of the mission.

4.3.3. Inference Attacks

Inference attacks involve extracting sensitive information from seemingly harmless data through correlation and analysis [206] - [210]. Attackers take advantage of vulnerabilities like inadequate data anonymization and a lack of privacy-preserving techniques. By studying patterns in the data, they can deduce sensitive details [211] that were not explicitly shared as shown in Figure 8, where Participant 1...k is considered as UAVs in a FANETs Architecture [212]. For instance, they might link UAV movements to specific objectives.

Figure 8 Interference Attack on FANETs Model

The consequences of inference attacks include the accidental disclosure of sensitive information, breaches of data privacy, and the compromise of mission integrity. Even without direct access to sensitive data, attackers can infer crucial details from patterns and correlations, leading to unintended exposure and undermining privacy.

4.3.4. Unauthorized Data Access

Unauthorized data access involves gaining access to sensitive information without proper authorization [213] - [215]. This can occur due to weak authentication mechanisms and inadequate access control policies. Attackers may use methods such as brute force attacks, exploiting default credentials, or exploiting vulnerabilities in access control systems to gain unauthorized entry. The impact of unauthorized data access includes the loss of sensitive data, breaches of data confidentiality, and the potential for data manipulation [216], [217]. Attackers can exploit these vulnerabilities to access critical data without authorization, manipulate the information, and use it for malicious purposes, thereby compromising the security and integrity of the FANETs Model [218] - [221].

5. Assessment of Current Privacy Solutions and Limitations

Current privacy solutions for FANETs focus on encryption, anonymous communication protocols, and secure data aggregation to protect sensitive information transmitted between UAVs and ground stations. Encryption techniques, such as AES and RSA, safeguard data against unauthorized access, while anonymous communication protocols hide the identities and locations of UAVs to prevent tracking and eavesdropping. Secure data aggregation ensures that only aggregated data, rather than raw data, is transmitted, reducing the risk of sensitive information leakage. However, these solutions face limitations due to the UAVs' constrained computational resources and energy supply, which make implementing complex cryptographic algorithms challenging. Additionally, the high mobility and dynamic topology of FANETs complicate the maintenance of robust privacy measures, necessitating ongoing research for more efficient and adaptable privacy-preserving techniques.

5.1. Data Breaches

Current solutions to mitigate data breaches involve the use of robust encryption techniques and access control mechanisms. These measures enhance data confidentiality and limit unauthorized access. However, encryption overhead and complex key management can be challenging for resource-limited UAVs, affecting their performance and operational efficiency [222], [223]. Despite their effectiveness in protecting data, the computational demands of encryption can lead to increased energy consumption and reduced operational time, posing a significant limitation for UAVs with limited resources [224] - [227].

5.2. Location Tracking

To counter location tracking, location obfuscation techniques and secure communication protocols are implemented. These methods protect the real-time location of UAVs, maintaining operational secrecy. However, obfuscation can impact the accuracy and efficiency of operations, making it necessary to balance privacy protection with operational needs [228] - [230]. The trade-off between maintaining the secrecy of UAV locations and ensuring precise and efficient mission execution remains a critical challenge that needs careful management [231]-[234].

5.3. Inference Attacks

Data anonymization and differential privacy techniques are used to mitigate inference attacks. These methods reduce the risk of sensitive information being inferred from data, ensuring better privacy protection [235]-[237]. However, balancing privacy and data utility remains a challenge, requiring careful consideration of both aspects. Ensuring that data remains useful for operational purposes while preventing sensitive information from being inferred is a complex task that often requires sophisticated algorithms and approaches [238], [239].

5.4. Unauthorized Data Access

Multi-factor authentication (MFA) and strict access control policies are deployed to prevent unauthorized data access [240] - [242]. These measures enhance the security of data access, ensuring that only authorized users can access sensitive information. However, MFA can be cumbersome and impact user experience, necessitating user-friendly solutions that do not compromise security [243]. Finding the right balance between security and usability is essential to ensure that these measures are effective without hindering operational efficiency. Table 5, provides a comprehensive summary of the limitations of the current privacy solutions

Table 5 Summary of Limitations

Limitation	Description
Adaptive Privacy Mechanisms	Existing solutions often lack the necessary adaptability to the dynamic nature of FANETs. Developing more flexible privacy mechanisms that can detect and respond to changing network conditions in real-time is crucial for continuous privacy protection.
Balancing Privacy and Performance	Ensuring robust privacy protection without compromising operational efficiency remains a significant challenge. Innovative solutions that balance privacy and performance, such as lightweight cryptographic algorithms and efficient privacy-preserving protocols, are needed
Integrating emerging technologies	Leveraging emerging technologies such as blockchain, AI, and machine learning for enhanced privacy protection in FANETs is still underexplored. Further research is needed to adapt and integrate these technologies effectively into FANETs.
User Awareness and Training	Ensuring that operators and users are aware of privacy best practices is crucial. Current research often overlooks the importance of user awareness and training, highlighting the need for comprehensive training programs and updated guidelines.

6. Performance issues in FANETs

Unique features that make FANETs advantageous also introduce several performance challenges. These challenges range from the high mobility of UAVs, limited bandwidth, susceptibility to interference, and resource constraints. Addressing these issues is crucial to ensuring the efficiency, reliability, and security of FANETs. This paper delves into four unique performance issues in FANETs, exploring how they occur and their impact on network performance, while highlighting the need for innovative solutions to overcome these challenges. Basically, performance issues in FANETs stem from the inherent characteristics of UAVs and the dynamic nature of the network. One primary challenge is maintaining stable and reliable communication links amidst constant changes in topology due to the high mobility of UAVs. This mobility can lead to frequent link breaks, resulting in packet loss, increased latency, and reduced throughput. Moreover, the aerial environment introduces unique factors such as varying altitudes, weather conditions, and obstacles that can affect signal propagation and communication quality. Efficient routing protocols are essential to adapt to these conditions, but their design is complicated by the need to balance responsiveness and resource consumption.

Additionally, the limited computational power and battery life of UAVs impose significant constraints on FANET performance. UAVs must perform multiple tasks, including communication, navigation, and data processing, within their limited energy budgets. High computational demands from complex algorithms can drain batteries quickly, reducing the operational lifespan of the network. This makes energy-efficient protocol design crucial to sustaining network performance over extended periods. Furthermore, the integration of heterogeneous UAVs with different capabilities and performance characteristics can complicate network management and optimization. Ensuring seamless interoperability and efficient resource utilization in such diverse environments remains a significant challenge for FANET performance enhancement.

6.1. Node Mobility and Network Partitioning

One significant performance issue in FANETs is network partitioning, caused by the high mobility of UAVs. In FANETs, UAVs constantly change positions, which can result in temporary disconnections and the formation of isolated subnetworks [244]. This phenomenon, known as network partitioning, severely impacts data routing efficiency and leads to increased latency and packet loss [245], [246]. As UAVs move away from each other or out of communication range, the network topology changes, causing disruptions in established communication paths. These disruptions necessitate frequent re-routing, consuming additional bandwidth and computational resources [247]. The dynamic nature of FANETs requires robust protocols that can quickly adapt to topology changes and minimize the negative impacts on network performance, such as delays in data transmission and reduced throughput.

6.2. Congestion and Bandwidth Limitations

Congestion in FANETs arises from the limited bandwidth available for communication among multiple UAVs. As the number of UAVs in the network increases, the demand for bandwidth grows, leading to congestion, especially when multiple UAVs attempt to transmit large volumes of data simultaneously [248]-[250]. This congestion results in higher latency and reduced data transmission rates, affecting the timely delivery of critical information [251], [252]. In scenarios where real-time data processing and rapid response are essential, such as disaster management or military

operations, congestion can lead to significant performance degradation. Effective congestion control mechanisms are necessary to manage bandwidth efficiently, ensuring smooth data flow and optimal network performance.

6.3. Interference and Signal Jamming

Interference and signal jamming are critical performance issues in FANETs, where adversaries intentionally disrupt communication channels to degrade network performance. Jamming attacks can be executed by transmitting high-power signals on the same frequencies used by FANETs, causing communication failures [253]. This results in increased packet loss, delayed transmissions, and in some cases, complete communication breakdowns. Signal jamming is particularly detrimental in FANETs due to the reliance on wireless communication for coordination and data exchange [254], [255]. Implementing robust anti-jamming techniques and adaptive frequency-hopping methods is crucial to maintaining reliable communication links and ensuring the network's resilience against such attacks.

6.4. Resource Constraints and Energy Consumption

UAVs in FANETs are typically constrained by limited onboard resources, particularly battery life and computational power [256], [257]. High energy consumption due to constant communication, data processing, and mobility can lead to rapid depletion of battery power, reducing the operational lifespan of UAVs. Resource-intensive tasks, such as encryption, routing, and real-time data processing, make more impact on performance [258], [259]. As UAVs exhaust their energy reserves, they may need to return to a base station for recharging, resulting in reduced network coverage and availability. Effective energy management strategies, such as optimizing communication protocols and utilizing energy-efficient hardware, are essential to prolong the operational duration of UAVs and maintain network performance.

7. Limitations and Gaps in Addressing Performance Issues in FANETs

Current routing protocols in FANETs struggle to adapt quickly to frequent topology changes, causing delays and increased packet loss, indicating a need for more adaptive and resilient algorithms to handle high mobility and prevent network partitioning [260]. Existing congestion control mechanisms are often ineffective in managing high data transmission demands, necessitating advanced techniques to optimize bandwidth usage and reduce latency during peak traffic [261]. Anti-jamming techniques currently fall short against sophisticated attacks, highlighting the requirement for more robust and adaptive strategies to maintain reliable communication despite interference [262]. Additionally, the high energy consumption due to constant communication and data processing rapidly depletes UAV batteries, underscoring the need for innovations in energy-efficient communication protocols and hardware to extend operational times and ensure sustained network performance [263], [264].

Table 6 below provides a summary of the limitations and the gaps identified.

Table 6 Performance Issues; Limitation, and Gaps

Performance Challenges	Limitations	Gaps
Node Mobility and Network Partitioning	Routing protocols struggle with frequent topology changes, causing delays and packet loss.	Need for more adaptive and resilient routing algorithms to handle high mobility.
Congestion and Bandwidth Limitations	Congestion control mechanisms are ineffective for high data transmission demands.	Development of advanced techniques to optimize bandwidth usage and reduce latency.
Interference and Signal Jamming	Current anti-jamming techniques may not protect against sophisticated jamming attacks.	Need for more robust and adaptive anti-jamming strategies.
Resource Constraints and Energy Consumption	High energy consumption depletes UAV batteries quickly.	Innovations in energy-efficient protocols and hardware to extend UAV operational times.

Addressing performance issues in FANETs is fraught with limitations and gaps, primarily due to the high mobility and dynamic topology of the network. Existing routing protocols often struggle to maintain consistent performance as UAVs move rapidly, frequently leading to broken links and increased packet loss. Traditional routing algorithms, designed for more static environments, cannot cope effectively with the rapid topology changes inherent in FANETs. Furthermore, while reactive protocols can adapt to these changes, they tend to introduce latency as new routes are discovered. Proactive protocols, on the other hand, consume significant resources to maintain up-to-date routing tables, exacerbating energy constraints and reducing the operational life of UAVs.

The limited computational power and energy resources of UAVs also present a significant challenge in addressing performance issues. Most UAVs have strict power budgets that must be shared across multiple functions, including communication, navigation, and sensing. Implementing advanced algorithms for routing, security, and data processing can quickly deplete these limited resources, leading to shorter mission durations and reduced network reliability. While some energy-efficient protocols have been proposed, they often sacrifice performance in terms of latency and throughput to conserve power. The challenge is to develop lightweight yet robust solutions that can strike a balance between resource consumption and network performance.

Another gap in addressing performance issues in FANETs is the integration and management of heterogeneous UAVs. FANETs often consist of UAVs with varying capabilities in terms of speed, altitude, communication range, and energy reserves. Coordinating these diverse assets to work seamlessly together is complex and requires advanced network management strategies. Additionally, environmental factors such as weather conditions and physical obstacles can further complicate communication and routing. Current research is exploring adaptive protocols and machine learning techniques to predict and mitigate these issues, but practical implementation remains challenging. There is a need for comprehensive frameworks that can dynamically adapt to the varying conditions and resource constraints while maintaining high performance and reliability in FANET operations.

7.1. Future research scopes

Future research in FANET security and privacy encompasses several promising areas aimed at enhancing the robustness, reliability, and confidentiality of these networks. Key areas include:

Advanced Cryptographic Techniques: Research into lightweight and energy-efficient cryptographic algorithms is crucial. These algorithms must provide robust security without overburdening the limited computational and power resources of UAVs. Future studies could focus on developing novel encryption methods tailored specifically for FANETs, balancing security with performance.

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS): Enhancing IDS tailored for FANETs to detect and mitigate various attacks, including spoofing, jamming, and DoS, is a vital area of research. Leveraging machine learning and artificial intelligence can help create adaptive and intelligent IDS capable of identifying new and evolving threats in real-time.

Secure Routing Protocols: Developing secure and efficient routing protocols that can dynamically adapt to the highly mobile and changing topology of FANETs is essential. These protocols need to ensure data integrity and confidentiality while maintaining high performance and reliability.

Privacy-Preserving Mechanisms: Research on privacy-preserving techniques such as anonymization, pseudonymization, and secure multi-party computation can help protect the identities and data of UAVs and users. These mechanisms should be lightweight to fit within the resource constraints of UAVs.

Blockchain Technology: Exploring the use of blockchain for decentralized and tamper-proof data management in FANETs can provide enhanced security and transparency. Blockchain can help ensure data integrity and facilitate secure communication and coordination among UAVs without relying on a central authority.

Quantum Cryptography: Investigating the potential of quantum cryptography to offer unparalleled security for FANETs is an exciting frontier. Although practical implementation may be years away, early research can lay the groundwork for integrating quantum-resistant algorithms in future UAV networks.

Resilience to Physical Layer Attacks: Studying methods to protect against physical layer attacks such as jamming and eavesdropping is crucial. Techniques like spread spectrum, frequency hopping, and advanced error correction codes can enhance the resilience of FANET communications.

Trust Management Systems: Developing robust trust management frameworks to ensure reliable interaction among UAVs is vital. These systems should dynamically assess the trustworthiness of nodes based on their behavior and communication patterns, adapting to the evolving network environment.

AI and Machine Learning for Security: Leveraging AI and machine learning to predict and respond to security threats dynamically can significantly enhance FANET security. These technologies can analyze vast amounts of data to detect anomalies and initiate proactive measures to counteract potential attacks.

Regulatory and Ethical Considerations: Researching the regulatory and ethical implications of FANET deployments can help address concerns related to privacy, data protection, and lawful usage. Establishing clear guidelines and frameworks will be essential as FANETs become more prevalent in civilian and commercial applications.

By addressing these research scopes, the future of FANET security and privacy can be significantly strengthened, ensuring safer and more reliable UAV networks for various critical applications.

8. Conclusion

The research has provided an in-depth analysis of the privacy and security issues in Flying Ad Hoc Networks (FANETs). Due to the highly dynamic and decentralized nature of these networks, FANETs pose unique challenges that distinguish them from traditional and terrestrial ad hoc networks. Deep analysis of current solutions demonstrates that while numerous approaches exist to mitigate threats in FANETs, each has its own set of strengths and limitations. Techniques such as encryption, secure routing protocols, and intrusion detection systems have shown effectiveness in specific scenarios; however, their applicability is often constrained by factors such as computational overhead, energy consumption, and the need for real-time operation in highly mobile environments. To bridge these gaps, future research must focus on developing innovative approaches tailored specifically to the unique demands of FANETs. Emphasis should be placed on lightweight cryptographic solutions that can operate efficiently in resource-constrained environments, as well as adaptive security frameworks that can dynamically respond to changing network conditions and threat landscapes. By addressing these gaps and exploring proposed future directions, researchers can contribute to the creation of more resilient and secure FANETs capable of operating in increasingly complex and adversarial environments.

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